

Proving the safety of a compiler with reference counting in Rocq using Iris

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Compiler safety guarantees that any well-formed input program is compiled into a target program that does not crash at runtime. By employing formal verification techniques like separation logic we can reason about and prove that a compiler meets these requirements.

In this paper, we present a modular safety proof for a compiler targeting a reference-counted concurrent language, using the Rocq proof assistant and the Iris separation logic framework. As part of our approach we formalize and verify the correctness of an atomic reference counter using separation logic and integrate it into the compiler's output to prove that it preserves safety, including memory correctness properties such the absence of use-after-free errors even in the presence of concurrency.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: compiler correctness, logical relations, separation logic, reference counting

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1 Introduction

Compilers transform a program from a language (usually a higher level one) into another, target language (usually a lower level one). One would expect the output of a compiler to have the same meaning as its input, a well behaving compiler should not be able to modify the behavior of programs. However compilers are not immune to bugs themselves, it is not unheard of for a compiler to compile a program incorrectly [24].

There have been various projects to formalize compiler correctness such as PureCake [11], CakeML [13], and CompCert [14]. These are large and complicated projects that took a lot of effort to complete but have been able to prove the correctness of the entire compilation pipeline, and are able to guarantee that their generated code will behave and produce the same results as the operational semantics of the source language instruct. In contrast, instead of trying to prove a "strong" correctness property in this paper we will focus on the concept of compiler *safety* specifically, which states that a target program will not get "stuck", without necessarily making any other guarantees regarding the behavior or exact value that the target program will produce. Safety is a weaker property, however it is easier to prove in a more scalable and straightforward way, and therefore has the potential to be use as a more practical and lightweight alternative to stronger properties.

Our objective is to prove the safety of a compiler from a language with automatic memory management, where said compiler links with and inserts calls to an atomic reference counting (ARC) library to its target output. In order to reason about our linked ARC library we want the specification for each function within the ARC library to be modular, so that we can easily reuse the ARC specification in our safety proof, as well as any other potential future proof that makes use of the ARC. In addition we want to avoid reasoning explicitly on top of the operational semantics as we find it to be a lot of effort and not particularly scalable. We do that by making use of concurrent separation logic, which is particularly suitable for achieving our goal given our requirements.

In order to achieve our goal we use the methods described in Wagner et al. [23]. We define our source language as well as a compiler specification that is capable of specifying a relation between (typed) source code and (untyped) target code. At the same time we define an ARC and verify it using separation logic. We then define a logical relation indexed over types in the source

language. We then make use of semantic typing [19], which by using the previously mentioned logical relation we can reason about the relation between target language expressions and source language types. This is an old technique that is seen as far back as Appel's work on Foundational Proof-Carrying Code [2]. We use the concept of semantic typing to then show that our semantically compiler preserves types, where if a source program has a certain type then the target program will have the same semantic type. From this theorem we can then derive a proof of safety. In addition we will also use semantic typing to show that different programs (as long as they are semantically typed in a suitable way) can be linked together safely.

In their paper Wagner et al. [23] make use of their own linear separation logic which makes use of custom modalities for reasoning about resources and a directed acyclic graph, which allows them to reason about nested structures and prove the lack of reference cycles, as well as leak-freedom. What motivated our work is the lack of a mechanized version of their proofs in theorem prover. In addition their use of a bespoke separation logic which was created solely for the verification of their ARC lacks various features that we can find in other logics such as invariants. This limits the ability to use existing separation logic frameworks or apply said separation logic for more complicated specifications.

We make use of the Iris [21] separation logic framework in order to formalize our work. Iris is a "battle-tested" separation logic framework for the Rocq proof assistant, with multiple successful projects being based on it, such as Rustbelt [9], RefinedC [20], and Diaframe [15]. By taking advantage of Iris we can avoid having to define our own version of separation logic in Rocq from scratch, which allows us to focus on our proofs. In addition it improves our capability of reusing our proofs and definitions, in addition to giving us the ability to potentially use the facilities that Iris provides to extend our separation logic in the future (such as by moving to a linear separation logic that ensures leak-freedom).

During our effort to integrate our ARC specification we decided on an unusual definition for our logical relation. More specifically while our logical relation relates source types with target values within an Iris proposition it also relates said values along with a fraction that denotes a "percentage of ownership" (called a fractional permission [6]). This also means that our logical relation does not only reason about the possible contents of the target value, but also about the current state of the heap.

The key points of our paper are as follows:

- We formalize a flexible ARC specification that is suitable for the definition of our logical relation and can be easily defined by using Iris's invariants and ghost state. (Sections 4 and 6)
- We provide a logical relation which by using separation logic is also able to reason about how much a value is owned in the current context (Section 5).
- We prove that all target programs produced by our compiler preserve the typing (through our use of semantic typing) of the input program. (Section 3, Theorem 3)
- We prove that we can safely "link" two semantically-typed programs in the target language, even if they were produced by different compilers. (Section 3, Theorem 5)
- We prove in a modular way that any compiler that complies with our specification will only produce safe code (which is memory safe, and does not get "stuck"). (Section 3, Lemma 1)
- Due to our use of Iris's separation logic we know that our compiler output is memory-safe (without use-after-free bugs, etc).

2 The languages and the compiler

In this section we introduce the high level functional source language **MyLang** (in blue) and **HeapLang** (in red) which acts as our low-level target language. Moreover we use blue for contexts, as they contain **MyLang** types.

2.1 Source language

We define **MyLang**'s syntax as follows:

$$t ::= \text{Nat} \mid \text{Bool} \mid \text{Unit} \mid t \rightarrow t \mid t \times t$$

$$\begin{aligned} e ::= & x \in \text{Var} \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \mid () \mid \text{true} \mid \text{false} \mid \\ & e \oplus e \mid \text{if } e \text{ then } e \text{ else } e \mid \\ & \text{rec } f(x : t) = e \mid e \ e \mid \\ & \text{new}(e, e) \mid \text{fst}(e) \mid \text{snd}(e) \mid \\ & \text{fork}(e) \mid \\ & \text{let } x := e \text{ in } e \end{aligned}$$

We want to draw attention to **new**(e_1, e_2) which creates a new pair, with **fst**(e) returning the first element and with **snd**(e) returning the second element. We compile **new**(e_1, e_2) to the target language by making use of memory allocation, through the use of an ARC. In addition concurrency is supported by **MyLang**, with **fork**(e) allowing the creation of a new thread. Different threads can not communicate with each other.

For the type system we use $\Gamma \vdash e : t$ to say that e has type t under context Γ and we define the following judgments:

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{DUP} \\ \frac{\Gamma, x : t_1 \vdash e : t_2 \quad (x, t_1) \in \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash e : t_2} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{DROP} \\ \frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1}{\Gamma, x : t_2 \vdash e : t_1} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{VAR} \\ x : t \vdash x : t \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{N-I} \\ \frac{n \in \mathbb{N}}{\vdash n : \text{Nat}} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{B-I} \\ \frac{b \in \mathbb{B}}{\vdash b : \text{Bool}} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{Unit-I} \\ \vdash () : \text{Unit} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LET} \\ \frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \quad \Gamma_2, x : t_1 \vdash e_2 : t_2 \quad x \notin \Gamma_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } x := e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : t_2} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{IF} \\ \frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \text{Bool} \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_3 : t}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{if } e_1 \text{ then } e_2 \text{ else } e_3 : t} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{REC} \\ \frac{f : t_1 \rightarrow t_2, x : t_1 \vdash e : t_2 \quad f \neq x}{\vdash \text{rec } f(x : t) = e : t_1 \rightarrow t_2} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{APP} \\ \frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t_1 \rightarrow t_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 \ e_1 : t_2} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{NEW} \\ \frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{new}(e_1, e_2) : t_1 \times t_2} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{FST} \\ \frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2}{\Gamma \vdash \text{fst}(e) : t_1} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{SND} \\ \frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2}{\Gamma \vdash \text{snd}(e) : t_2} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \text{FORK} \\ \frac{\Gamma \vdash e : ()}{\Gamma \vdash \text{fork}(e) : ()} \end{array}$$

We roughly follow the typing scheme from Wagner et al. [23]. We omit the typing rules for the binary operators (\oplus) from this paper as they are quite standard, although we include them in our Rocq formalization.

Our typing context Γ is represented as a multiset, where for any variable name x it can map to a **MyLang** type t any number of times. We do this because our intention is to keep track of the different amount of copies that each variable has. Therefore we do not allow for a variable name to map to two different types at the same time (when creating a typing derivation for an expression starting with the empty context). This is done by enforcing constraints on the context in **LET** by requiring $x \notin \Gamma_2$ and by enforcing an empty context in **REC**.

For simplicity reasons, just like in the paper by Wagner et al. [23] we only consider functions which do not capture a closure and require an empty environment, we discuss more about it in Section 8.

2.2 Target language

We are compiling to a subset of Iris's **HeapLang** [21]. **HeapLang** is similar to **MyLang** except it is an untyped language with support for manual memory management. It also has the ability to store "bigger" constructs (such as potentially nested pairs, which work similar to structs in C and are therefore not allocated but instead stored in the stack) in a single memory location.

In order to simulate how things would work with a low-level language (such as C) we pose a restriction to ourselves where we will not allow the ability to store nested pairs within a memory cell and in order to store more elements we have to make use of memory allocation.

HeapLang includes the ability to atomically modify memory cells by using the **FAA** (Fetch-and-add) instruction. This instruction will atomically add a value to a memory cell and then return the previous value. We can also allocate memory with **AllocN**(n) which gives us an array of size n containing "poison" to signify that the elements of the array are uninitialized (which is a value that does not have a defined reduction for various operations - such as addition), and subsequently free it with **Free**. In addition it has the capacity to store a value to a memory cell and fetch it ($e \leftarrow e$ and $!e$). **HeapLang** also provides tagged-unions (**Some**(e) and **None**) which are eliminated using the **match** construct and are stored in the stack. Finally **fork** $\{e\}$ is used to spawn a new thread that executes the expression given to it.

We define our subset of **HeapLang**'s syntax as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v &::= n \in \mathbb{N} \mid () \mid \mathbf{true} \mid \mathbf{false} \mid \mathbf{rec} \ f \ x = e \mid (v, v) \mid \mathbf{Some}(v) \mid \mathbf{None} \\
 e &::= x \in \mathbf{var} \mid v \mid e \oplus e \mid \mathbf{if} \ e \ \mathbf{then} \ e \ \mathbf{else} \ e \mid \\
 &\quad e \ e \mid \mathbf{let} \ x = e \ \mathbf{in} \ e \mid \\
 &\quad \mathbf{AllocN}(n) \mid e \leftarrow e \mid !e \mid \mathbf{FAA}(e, e) \mid \mathbf{Free}(e) \mid \\
 &\quad \mathbf{fst}(e) \mid \mathbf{snd}(e) \mid \\
 &\quad \mathbf{match} \ e \ \mathbf{with} \ \mathbf{Some}(x) \Rightarrow e \mid \mathbf{None} \Rightarrow e \ \mathbf{end} \mid \\
 &\quad \mathbf{fork} \ \{e\}
 \end{aligned}$$

In addition to the above we define $\lambda x.e$ to be syntactic sugar for $\mathbf{rec} \ f \ x = e$, and $e';e$ to be syntactic sugar for $\mathbf{let} \ y = e' \ \mathbf{in} \ e$ with the additional constraint that f and y does not appear free in e .

The operational semantics for **HeapLang** are defined as one would expect in terms of small-step semantics with support for multiple threads.

2.3 Compiler specification

Just like in Wagner et al. [23] instead of defining a compiler as a computable function we instead define a compiler specification as an inductive predicate $\Gamma \vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e'$ which says that given a typing judgment $\Gamma \vdash e : t$ the **HeapLang** output is e' . This makes our compiler specification directed by the typing derivations. We then formulate our proofs on the specification instead of a specific compiler implementation.

In order to define our compiler specification we first declare which types can simply be duplicated at any point without the involvement of memory allocation or the ARC (this is similar to Rust's Copy trait [12]). The only type of whose values can not be trivially copied is the pair type, as it is the only type which makes use of memory allocation. Values of simple types like **Nat** are unboxed, while values of the function type are function pointers as **MyLang** does not have closures.

Type	Copyable
Nat	Yes
Bool	Yes
Unit	Yes
$t_1 \rightarrow t_2$	Yes
$t_1 \times t_2$	No

The compiler specification is defined as such:

$$\frac{\text{DUP-NC-C} \quad \Gamma, x : t_2 \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad (x, t_2) \in \Gamma \quad \neg\text{Copy}(t_2)}{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{clone } x; e'}$$

$$\frac{\text{DUP-C-C} \quad \Gamma, x : t_2 \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad (x, t_2) \in \Gamma \quad \text{Copy}(t_2)}{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e'}$$

$$\frac{\text{DROP-C} \quad \Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e'}{\Gamma, x : t_2 \vdash e : t_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{drop}_{T_2} x; e'}$$

$$\text{VAR-C} \quad x : t \vdash x : t \rightsquigarrow x$$

$$\frac{\text{N-C} \quad n \in \mathbb{N}}{\vdash n : \text{Nat} \rightsquigarrow n}$$

$$\frac{\text{B-C} \quad b \in \mathbb{B}}{\vdash b : \text{Bool} \rightsquigarrow b}$$

$$\text{UNIT-C} \quad \vdash () : \text{Unit} \rightsquigarrow ()$$

$$\frac{\text{LET-C} \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \quad \Gamma_2, x : t_1 \vdash e_2 : t_2 \rightsquigarrow e'_2 \quad x \notin \Gamma_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } x := e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : t_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e'_2}$$

$$\frac{\text{IF-C} \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \text{Bool} \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t \rightsquigarrow e'_2 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_3 : t \rightsquigarrow e'_3}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{if } e_1 \text{ then } e_2 \text{ else } e_3 : t \rightsquigarrow \text{if } e'_1 \text{ then } e'_2 \text{ else } e'_3}$$

$$\frac{\text{REC-C} \quad f : t_1 \rightarrow t_2, x : t_1 \vdash e : t_2 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad f \neq x}{\vdash \text{rec } f(x : t) = e : t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{rec } f x = e'}$$

$$\frac{\text{APP-C} \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \rightsquigarrow e'_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 e_1 : t_2 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 e'_2}$$

$$\frac{\text{NEW-C} \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : t_1 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : t_2 \rightsquigarrow e'_2}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{new}(e_1, e_2) : t_1 \times t_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{newarc}(e'_1, e'_2)}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{FST-C-C} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad \text{Copy}(t_1)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fst}(e) : t_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{let } r = e' \mathbf{ in let } v = \mathbf{load } r \mathbf{ in dropT}_{t_1 \times t_2} r; \mathbf{fst}(v)} \\
\\
\text{FST-NC-C} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad \neg\text{Copy}(t_1)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fst}(e) : t_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{let } r = e' \mathbf{ in let } v = \mathbf{load } r \mathbf{ in clone } v; \mathbf{dropT}_{t_1 \times t_2} r; \mathbf{fst}(v)} \\
\\
\text{SND-C-C} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad \text{Copy}(t_2)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{snd}(e) : t_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{let } r = e' \mathbf{ in let } v = \mathbf{load } r \mathbf{ in dropT}_{t_1 \times t_2} r; \mathbf{snd}(v)} \\
\\
\text{SND-NC-C} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : t_1 \times t_2 \rightsquigarrow e' \quad \neg\text{Copy}(t_2)}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{snd}(e) : t_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{let } r = e' \mathbf{ in let } v = \mathbf{load } r \mathbf{ in clone } v; \mathbf{dropT}_{t_1 \times t_2} r; \mathbf{snd}(v)} \\
\\
\text{FORK-C} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{Unit} \rightsquigarrow e'}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fork}(e) : \mathbf{Unit} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{fork } \{e'\}}
\end{array}$$

We make special distinctions for rules that insert calls to `clone`, where if the type of the value to be cloned is copyable said calls are skipped. Whenever there is a `DUP` or a `DROP` rule in the type derivation we explicitly insert calls to `clone` and `dropTt` in order to duplicate or drop references respectively. Note that `dropTt` is a Rocq-level function that is parametrized over `MyLang`'s types in order to be able to drop pairs that are multiple levels deep. We explain how these functions work in Section 2.4. We do not need anything similar to `dropTt` for `clone` as we have special rules for copyable types that do not insert the call to `clone` (such as `DUP-C-C`).

In our specification all `MyLang` variable names are mapped without modification into `HeapLang` variables.

We have distinct version of various rules for copyable types (`DUP-C-C`, `FST-C-C`, `SND-C-C`) and their non-copyable variants (`DUP-NC-C`, `FST-NC-C`, `SND-NC-C`). The `C` in the rule name stands for *Copyable*, while `NC` stands for *Non-Copyable*. The non-copyable rules are identical with their copyable versions with the exception that they insert calls to `clone`.

Previously we mentioned that the `DUP` and `DROP` rules correspond directly with calls to `clone` and `drop`. One may notice that each compilation rule corresponds to one (or two, if there is a copyable and non-copyable distinction in the rule) typing rule. This was also the reasoning behind the choice of a substructural type system, that way we are able to define the compiler specification in a way that is completely driven by the typing derivation.

The rule `NEW-C` converts potentially nested `MyLang` pairs into calls that allocate a new ARC. So something like `new(e1, new(e2, e3))` would be compiled into `newarc(e'1, newarc(e'2, e'3))`, which in turn when executed would allocate two separate ARCs.

An important part of our compiler specification are the rules for fetching the pair elements (`FST-C-C`, `FST-NC-C`, `SND-C-C`, `SND-NC-C`). We make use of two separate `let` expressions. First we store the compiled version (e') of the expression (e) that is given to the command so that said expression is executed a single time. Afterwards then we load and assign to another variable the value that is stored within it. Then in the non-copyable variants we `clone` the loaded value, and we continue by dropping the original value using `dropTt`. The reason that our specification clones the inner value is that if for example we have a nested pair, calling `dropTt` on the outer pair will

not deallocate the pair that we just loaded. Meanwhile copyable types are not ever deallocated so they do not need any special treatment. As a final step we call the **HeapLang** pair eliminator on the loaded value. All this allows us to implement pairs in such a way that will not leave memory leaks nor will allow for values that are still in use to be dropped.

We continue by formalizing the relation between the typing derivation and the compiler specification. We claim that any compiler that adheres to our compiler specification will be able to compile any well-typed program. In addition any program that can be compiled by said compiler will be well-typed.

THEOREM 1 (WELL-TYPED EXPRESSIONS CAN BE COMPILED). *Given a typing derivation $\Gamma \vdash e : t$ there exists an expression e' such that $\Gamma \vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e'$ holds.*

We prove this by induction on the type derivation.

THEOREM 2 (TYPE DERIVATION EXTRACTION). *If $\Gamma \vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e'$ then $\Gamma \vdash e : t$*

We prove this by induction on the compiler specification.

Finally we define what it means for a compiler to be compliant to our specification. In this paper we do not define such a compiler as it would go beyond our scope. Implementing such a compiler is somewhat tricky as it would also need to act as the type checker as well. However we believe that defining such a compiler is indeed possible as we took great care when defining our compiler specification.

DEFINITION 1 (COMPLIANT COMPILER). *We say that a compiler $f : \text{expr} \rightarrow \text{expr}$ is compliant to our specification if given $\vdash e : t$ there exists a proof that $\vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow f(e)$ holds.*

2.4 ARC Implementation

Our ARC consists of the following operations: `newarc`, `clone`, `drop`, `load`. See Fig. 1 for their definitions. In order to create an instance of our ARC we use `newarc v` which initializes a new ARC with a reference count of 1 and stores the value `v` in it. We provide a visual representation of the memory layout of an ARC (where n is the counter).

$$\begin{aligned} \ell &\mapsto \boxed{n} \\ \ell + 1 &\mapsto \boxed{v} \end{aligned}$$

To increment or decrement the reference count, we use `clone x` and `drop x`, respectively. Both functions rely on the atomic instruction **FAA** to fetch and increase the reference count in order to ensure safe concurrent `clone` and `drop` implementations.

If the reference count reaches 1, calling `drop x` will perform a shallow deallocation and return the value stored within the ARC, releasing it into its caller.

To retrieve the value stored in the ARC without modifying the reference count, we use `load x`.

In addition to the above we also define `dropTt` (see Fig. 2 which is a Rocq-level function defined recursively over a **MyLang** type. Its job is to perform a deep deallocation by recursively calling `drop` on nested pairs. If it is given a pair it will go over its elements if this was the last reference to it.

3 Overview of approach

Our goal is to prove that the result of a compilation is *safe*, this means that our program should never get "stuck". I.e. after any amount of evaluation steps, an expression `e` should either be a value or be able to step again.

```

newarc  $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  let  $\ell = \text{AllocN}(2)$  in
     $\ell \leftarrow 1;$ 
     $(\ell + 1) \leftarrow x;$ 
     $\ell$ 

clone  $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  FAA( $x, 1$ ); ()

load  $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  !( $x + 1$ )

drop  $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  if FAA( $x, -1$ ) = 1 then
    let  $y = !(\mathbf{x} + 1)$  in
    Free( $x$ )
    Free( $x + 1$ )
    Some( $y$ )
else
    None

```

Fig. 1. ARC Implementation

```

dropT $_{t_1 \times t_2}$   $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  match  $x$  with
    inl $_v$   $\_ \Rightarrow$  ()
    | inr $_v$   $y \Rightarrow$  dropT $_{t_1}$  fst( $y$ ); dropT $_{t_2}$  snd( $y$ )
end

dropT $_t$   $\triangleq$   $\lambda x.$  () (if  $t \neq t_1 \times t_2$ )

```

Fig. 2. dropT $_t$ implementation

DEFINITION 2 (**HEAPLANG SAFETY**).

$$\text{safe}(e) \triangleq \forall \vec{e}_2, \sigma, \sigma_2. (e, \sigma) \rightsquigarrow^* (\vec{e}_2, \sigma_2) \rightarrow e_2 \in \text{val} \vee \exists e_3, \sigma_3. (e_2, \sigma_2) \rightsquigarrow (e_3, \sigma_3)$$

Attempting to prove that $\vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e$ implies $\text{safe}(e)$ directly by using naive induction would give us an inductive hypothesis that would be too weak. Our approach instead will be to introduce an intermediate goal that claims that all well-typed programs in **HeapLang** are safe (Theorem 3).

However, as we noted previously in Section 2.2 **HeapLang** is an *untyped* language, so our notion for typing would have to be slightly different. Just like in Wagner et al. [23] we make use of a technique called semantic typing, of which a clear description can be found in Timany et al. [22].

We recall that the syntactic typing judgment for typing in **MyLang** has the following notation: $\Gamma \vdash e : t$. The notation for semantic typing in **HeapLang** is similar to syntactic typing and is written as such: $\Gamma \models e : t$. We define our notion of semantic typing later at Definition 6.

The difference with syntactic typing is that whereas syntactic typing is defined for **MyLang** as an inductive predicate without concern for the operational semantics of the language, semantic typing is defined as a proposition with regards to the result of an evaluation of **HeapLang**. More specifically, semantic typing states that any evaluation of e under context Γ if it terminates will

result in a value which satisfies a logical relation indexed by t (see Definition 4). We elaborate more about this in Section 5.

THEOREM 3 (FUNDAMENTAL THEOREM). *If $\Gamma \vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e'$ then $\Gamma \models e' : t$.*

We prove this by induction on the compiler specification, we make sure to use our ARC specification for whenever calls to ARC functions occur. After proving this we are halfway to our goal, we then prove that all semantically typed **HeapLang** programs under the empty context fulfill our definition of safety.

THEOREM 4 (ADEQUACY). *If $\Gamma \models e : t$ then e is safe.*

We prove this by using the **HeapLang** adequacy theorem.

Finally we use the above theorems to state that any compiler that fulfills our compiler specification is in fact safe.

THEOREM 5 (COMPILER SAFETY). *If $\vdash e : t \rightsquigarrow e'$ then e' is safe.*

We prove safety by combining the fundamental theorem with Theorem 4.

In addition we prove that if two target-language expressions are semantically typed in a suitable way we can link them together such that the result will remain semantically typed. This property is interesting because the two expressions do not need to come from the same compiler, in fact, one of the expressions could even be manually written by a programmer, it only matters whether the expressions are semantically typed. This is because the way that our semantic typing relation describes the "behavior" and the resulting value of said expressions is enough to reason about the semantic type of the resulting expression as well. For example e_1 could have been the result of our compiler defined in Section 2.3 and e_2 could have been produced by a completely different compiler, as long as it also produces semantically typed target code. In addition, by using Adequacy (Theorem 4) we can prove that the linked result is safe if it's a closed expression.

LEMMA 1 (LINKING). *If $\Gamma_1 \models e_1 : t_1$ and $\Gamma_2, x : t_1 \models e_2 : t_2$ then $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \models \mathbf{let } x = e_1 \mathbf{ in } e_2 : t_2$.*

Can be easily proven similar to the let case in Theorem 3.

4 ARC specification

We formalize the specification for our ARC in terms of Hoare triples [8]. In simple terms a triple $\{P\} e \{v, \Phi(v)\}$ claims that in order to execute e the precondition P needs to hold. After e is executed it will either not terminate or it will return a value v , and as our postcondition the predicate $\Phi(v)$ will need to hold. More specifically we make use of separation logic [16] a framework based on the logic of bunched implications [17] which introduces concepts such as the separating conjunction $P * Q$. This conjunction asserts that P and Q hold for disjoint portions of memory. Separation logic allows us to reason about resource ownership and independent memory regions making it particularly useful for reasoning about concurrency. Here we provide the syntax for a subset of Iris's separation logic:

$$P ::= P * P \mid P * P \mid l \mapsto_q v \mid P \vee P \mid \forall x. P \mid \exists x. P \mid \top \mid \perp \mid \triangleright P \mid \Box P \mid \mathbf{wp } e \{v, P\} \mid \dots$$

We have $\mathbf{wp } e \{v, P\}$, "wp" stands for "weakest precondition". It basically says that for any possible evaluation of e if it terminates with a value v then P should hold. Hoare triples in Iris are defined in terms of wp. More specifically, $\{P\} e \{v, P\}$ would be defined similarly to $\Box(P * \mathbf{wp } e \{v, P\})$.

We have the ability to express statements that hold independently of the heap and can be duplicated at any point by using the \Box modality (the "always" modality). We can also express

statements that hold only after an evaluation step has been taken by using the \triangleright modality (the "later" modality). In addition to that the "wand" connective ($P \multimap Q$) states that by consuming a resource of type P from our current context, we can produce a Q (i.e. $P * (P \multimap Q) \vdash Q$). Finally we have $l \mapsto_q v$ which are maps from locations to values. We note that the separation logic used in Iris is affine, which means that resources may be discarded at will (The following holds: $P * Q \vdash P$), which makes proving leak-freedom non-trivial and as a result it is not one of the properties that we aim to prove.

We make use of a concept known as fractional permissions [6, 7] which allows us to split certain resources into multiple parts, each under a certain fraction. It also allows us to unite resources back into one. The main idea behind fractional permissions is that a resource with a permission of 1 is "fully owned" in the current context and any other value means that the resource is only partially owned.

DEFINITION 3 (FRACTIONAL PREDICATES). *Given $\Phi : (0, 1] \rightarrow iProp$ we say that Φ is fractional if and only if for any p, q where $p + q \in (0, 1]$, $\Phi(p + q) \dashv\vdash \Phi(p) * \Phi(q)$ holds.*

An example of a fractional proposition is the mapping of a location to a value ($l \mapsto_q v$). We can perform destructive operations on it (such as freeing or modifying it) only if we completely "own" the resource (only if $q = 1$). This allows us for example to split a resource between two threads and be sure that neither thread will attempt to free the resource (therefore avoiding use-after-free bugs).

This is required for our proof of **LOAD-SPEC** and **CONV**, we will elaborate on this in Section 6 but the general idea is that in order to load the value that is stored within the ARC, we *split* the fractional proposition $\Phi(v, q)$ into two parts, one which is given to the program through **LOAD-SPEC** and one which remains inside the ARC (for future calls to load).

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{NEWARC-SPEC} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{CLONE-SPEC} \\
 \{ \Phi v 1 \} \text{newarc } v \{ a. \text{arc } \Phi a 1 \} \qquad \{ \text{arc } \Phi a q_a \} \text{clone } a \{ \text{arc } \Phi a q_a * \text{arc } \Phi a 1 \} \\
 \\
 \text{DROP-SPEC} \\
 \{ \text{arc } \Phi a 1 \} \text{drop } a \{ v. \exists v'. \text{if } v = \text{inr}_v(v') \text{ then } \Phi v' 1 \text{ else } \top \} \\
 \\
 \text{LOAD-SPEC} \\
 \frac{\text{Fractional}(\Phi)}{\{ \text{arc } \Phi a q_a \} \text{load } a \{ v. \exists q_v. \Phi v q_v * \text{arcborrow } \Phi a q_a v q_v \}} \\
 \\
 \text{CONV} \\
 \frac{\text{Fractional}(\Phi)}{\Phi v q_v * \text{arcborrow } \Phi a q_a v q_v \equiv * \text{arc } \Phi a q_a}
 \end{array}$$

In our definitions Φ acts as the predicate which represents the semantic type of the value that the ARC is holding. In our proofs that use our ARC specifications we initialize it with our logical relation which we will define in Definition 4.

Calling `load a` extracts the value stored within the ARC. By using **LOAD-SPEC** we receive a value v that satisfies $\Phi v q_v$ and `arcborrow $\Phi a q_a v q_v$` . Here a is the ARC that we "borrowed" and extracted a portion from. q_a is the total percentage of a that we own, and q_v is the borrowed percentage (where $q_v < q_a$). We can return any borrowed data back into the ARC by using **CONV**.

We note that `arc` is fractional, which allows us to use nested ARCs. We explain why we include v and Φ in `arcborrow` in Section 6.

Examples. In order to demonstrate how our ARC works we offer the following examples, with Φ defined as $\lambda v. \exists n \in \mathbb{N}. v = n$:

```

{⊤}
let  $x = \text{newarc}(\text{newarc } 0)$  in
{arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1}
  clone( $x$ );
{arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1 * arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1}
  fork {drop( $x$ )};
{arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1}
  let  $y = \text{load } x$  in
{arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $q_v$  * arcborrow (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1  $v$   $q_v$ }
  clone  $y$ ;
{arc  $\Phi$   $y$  1 * arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $q_v$  * arcborrow (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1  $v$   $q_v$ }
{arc  $\Phi$   $y$  1 * arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1} (by CONV)
  drop( $x$ );
{arc  $\Phi$   $y$  1}
  drop( $y$ );
{⊤}

```

```

{arc (arc  $\Phi$ )  $x$  1}
drop  $x$ 
{⊤}

```

In this example clone provides us with an additional arc in our context, which represents the increment to the reference counter. Fork splits our execution into two parts, we move the expression argument to fork (as well as part of our context) to the right in order to show the new thread, which all it does is attempt to free the ARC resource, which is completely owned by it. Meanwhile the main thread continues by loading the value stored within the ARC.

We provide another example to showcase what would happen if we did not use clone instead. Since **DROP-SPEC** requires a fully-owned ARC, we would be unable to drop it as we can see in the following example:

```

{⊤}
let  $x = \text{newarc } 0$  in
{arc  $\Phi$   $x$  1}
{arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $\frac{1}{2}$  * arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $\frac{1}{2}$ } (by Definition 3)
  fork { $e$ };
{arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $\frac{1}{2}$ } | {arc  $\Phi$   $x$   $\frac{1}{2}$ }
  ...      |  $e$ 

```

Note that here we will never be able to free our ARC as different threads can not communicate, and therefore the two arc will never be in the same context again, which means that we can not unite them into a fully owned ARC.

5 Semantic typing

In order to reason about whether programs in **HeapLang** "semantically behave" similar to the type in **MyLang** (as in, they preserve the semantic interpretation of the type) we make use of a technique known as semantic typing. The usual way to do this would be to start by defining a logical relation that maps types to sets of values, however we make use of a slightly different logical

relation. Our logical relation $\llbracket t \rrbracket : \mathbf{val} \rightarrow (0, 1] \rightarrow iProp$ relates **MyLang** types with **HeapLang** values along with fractional permissions within an Iris context, so at the same time it allows us to reason about the current state of the heap. A way to interpret $\llbracket t \rrbracket v 1$ is that the completely owned value v semantically has type t .

DEFINITION 4 (SEMANTIC TYPES).

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \mathbf{Nat} \rrbracket v q &\triangleq \exists n \in \mathbb{N}. v = n \\ \llbracket \mathbf{Bool} \rrbracket v q &\triangleq \exists b \in \mathbb{B}. v = b \\ \llbracket \mathbf{Unit} \rrbracket v q &\triangleq v = () \\ \llbracket t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \rrbracket v q &\triangleq \Box \forall w_1. \llbracket t_1 \rrbracket (w_1, 1) * wp v w_1 \{ w_2. \llbracket t_2 \rrbracket (w_2, 1) \} \\ \llbracket t_1 \times t_2 \rrbracket v q &\triangleq \text{arc} (\lambda w. p. \exists w_1, w_2 \in \mathbf{Val}. w = (w_1, w_2) * \llbracket t_1 \rrbracket w_1 p * \llbracket t_2 \rrbracket (w_2, p)) v q \end{aligned}$$

The semantic interpretation $\llbracket t \rrbracket$ of all types (except for the case that t is the pair type) is Persistent (Definition 5). Persistence is a property from Iris [10] that we use as the semantic dual of copyable types as we defined in Section 2.3. We use the persistence property for types that are not boxed, as it lets us use them an unlimited amount of times, without having to wrap them within an ARC and manually duplicate them using `clone`. More specifically, a proposition is persistent if we can put it under the always modality at will.

DEFINITION 5 (PERSISTENCE). *Given a proposition $P : iProp$ we say that P is persistent if $P \vdash \Box P$*

A proposition which is under the always modality can be duplicated $\Box P \vdash \Box P * \Box P$ and can also have its always modality removed $\Box P \vdash P$.

LEMMA 2 (COPYABLE TYPES ARE SEMANTICALLY PERSISTENT). *Given a type t , a value v , and a $q \in (0, 1]$, if t is a copyable type, then $\llbracket t \rrbracket v q$ is persistent.*

We prove the above lemma by performing a case-analysis on t . For the cases of **Nat**, **Bool**, and **Unit** it is trivial as it is just an existential over a pure proposition. For the case of $t_1 \rightarrow t_2$ we can prove that it is persistent as it is quantified under the \Box modality which is persistent by definition.

As we saw before **LOAD-SPEC** requires a fractional predicate to describe the semantic type of the value within the ARC. Since we initialize said predicate with our logical relation we prove that $\llbracket t \rrbracket$ is Fractional (Definition 3).

LEMMA 3 (SEMANTIC TYPES ARE FRACTIONAL). *Given a type t and a value v , $\llbracket t \rrbracket v$ is fractional*

We prove this by simple case analysis on t .

- For the copyable types, since the fraction is not used while at the same time we can duplicate them at will we can infer that they are indeed fractional.
- For the pair type, we use the fact that `arc` is always fractional regardless of its Φ , which we prove in Lemma 4.

Now that we have defined our logical relation, we are able to define the Hoare triple for `dropTt` as follows:

$$\text{DROPT-SPEC} \\ \{ \llbracket t \rrbracket v 1 \} \text{drop}_{T_t} v \{ (). \top \}$$

Finally we define the relation for semantic typing. In order to claim that e has semantically the type t under a context Γ we mean that if we substitute all variables in Γ that occur freely in e with values that satisfy the semantic interpretation of their associated type, then after evaluating the resulting expression the result will satisfy the semantic interpretation of t .

DEFINITION 6 (SEMANTIC TYPING RELATION).

$$\Gamma \models e : t := \forall \vec{v}. \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket(\vec{v}, 1) \vdash \text{wp } e[\vec{v}]\{\text{w}. \llbracket t \rrbracket(\text{w}, 1)\}$$

(where \vec{v} is a map that associates variable names to values)

We use our semantic typing relation in order to prove the fundamental theorem (Theorem 3) for our compiler, and that way we can ensure that our compiler semantically preserves the type of its input. In addition it allows us to define a suitable adequacy theorem (Theorem 4) which allows us to prove safety (Theorem 5).

6 ARC proof

In order to prove the correctness of our specification for our ARC we first define $\text{arc } \Phi \ v \ q_v$ and $\text{arcborrow } \Phi \ v \ q_v \ w \ q_w$. Within these definition we make use of various concepts from Iris. Specifically we use invariants, resource algebras, ghost variables, and meta tokens. [10]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{arcinv}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \Phi, \ell) &\triangleq \exists n \in \mathbb{N}, v, q_v \in (0, 1], q_b \in [0, 1]. \\ &\quad \gamma_1 \overset{\bullet}{\hookrightarrow}_1 n * \\ &\quad ((\gamma_2 \overset{\bullet}{\hookrightarrow}_n q_b * \\ &\quad \quad \ell \mapsto n * \\ &\quad \quad \ell + 1 \mapsto v * \\ &\quad \quad \Phi \ v \ q_v * \\ &\quad \quad \gamma_3 \overset{\bullet}{\hookrightarrow}_{0.5} v * \\ &\quad \quad n \geq 1 \wedge q_v + q_b = 1) \\ &\quad \vee n = 0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{arc } \Phi \ a \ q_a &\triangleq \exists v, \pi \in (0, 1], \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3. \\ &\quad a \in \text{Loc} \\ &\quad \text{meta}(a, \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3) \\ &\quad \boxed{\text{arcinv}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \Phi, a)} * \\ &\quad \gamma_1 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_\pi q_a * \\ &\quad \gamma_2 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{q_a} 0 * \\ &\quad \gamma_3 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{\pi+2} v \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{arcborrow } \Phi \ a \ q_a \ v \ q_v &\triangleq \exists \pi \in (0, 1], \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3. \\ &\quad a \in \text{Loc} \\ &\quad \text{meta}(a, \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3) \\ &\quad \boxed{\text{arcinv}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \Phi, a)} * \\ &\quad \gamma_1 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_\pi q_a * \\ &\quad \gamma_2 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{q_a} q_v * \\ &\quad \gamma_3 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{\pi+2} v \end{aligned}$$

An invariant of the form \boxed{P} is an opaque property which states that we know P to be true and has to remain true throughout the program's execution after being established. We have the ability to allocate an invariant and open an invariant (which gives us the obligation to close it afterwards).

Opening the invariant will provide in our context the proposition P held within the invariant. Once an invariant has been opened it has to be closed after the next operation (which has to be atomic) has been executed. In order to close the invariant we need to prove that said proposition still holds. In our specific use-case for example we are not allowed to simply free the ARC after opening the invariant without the counter being decremented as we would not be able to close the invariant afterwards.

In Iris some resources are named. This is a way to distinguish between different resources of the same type. We signify a name as γ_n . Each new named resource is created with a unique name that has not been used before. In our definition of `arc` and `arcborrow` we existentially quantify over these names. Doing this naively would pose the problem that our definition for `arc` would not be fractional. To avoid this issue we make use of meta tokens. A meta token $\text{meta}(\ell, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n)$ associates a location with a set of names. The way it works is that originally when allocating a location we get a meta token $\text{metatoken}(\ell)$ for which the following rule holds: $\forall \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n. \text{metatoken}(\ell) * \Box \text{meta}(\ell, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n)$. In simple terms this states that by consuming a $\text{metatoken}(\ell)$ we can produce a persistent association between a location and set of names. Then in our proof of fractionality for `arc` we use another rule which states that a location only has a single set of associated names: $\text{meta}(\ell, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n) * \text{meta}(\ell, \gamma'_1, \dots, \gamma'_n) * \gamma_1 = \gamma'_1 * \dots * \gamma_n = \gamma'_n$. This allows us to make sure that the resource names are constant for each ARC without explicitly naming them as an argument, which would mean that our `arc` Φ would not have a suitable type for use as a semantic type. Note that in **HeapLang** each location will be fresh, even if previous locations have been freed, so it is not possible to associate a location with two different names.

Similarly in order to "synchronize" the variable held within the existential quantification of our invariant we make use of ghost variables which we use in order to synchronize the contents of an opened invariant with the "outside world".

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{G-CREATE} \\
 \exists \gamma. \gamma \hookrightarrow_1 v \\
 \\
 \text{G-UPDATE} \\
 \gamma \hookrightarrow_1 v \multimap \gamma \hookrightarrow_1 w \\
 \\
 \text{G-AGREE} \\
 \gamma \hookrightarrow_p v * \gamma \hookrightarrow_q w \multimap v = w \\
 \\
 \text{G-FRACTIONAL} \\
 \gamma \hookrightarrow_{p+q} v \dashv\vdash \gamma \hookrightarrow_p v * \gamma \hookrightarrow_q v
 \end{array}$$

Finally we utilize fractional authoritative cameras. Both ghost variables and fractional authoritative cameras are formalized on top of resource algebras, instead of being axiomatized in the logic itself. The core idea of fractional authoritative cameras is that we have an authoritative view ($\bullet_p v$) and one or more fragments ($\circ_q w$). Here q is a portion of p and w is a portion of b . The total of all fragments sums up to that of the authoritative fragment. The only requirement placed upon the values stored within the fractional authoritative cameras is that they need to be communicative monoids. Some of the rules (such as **A-UPDATE-SURPLUS-CANCEL**) also require that they are cancelable (which basically means having the ability to subtract in the case of fractions in $(0, 1]$). In our case we make use of two distinct authoritative views. One synchronizes the counter, and the other uses the counter as the fraction in order to reason about borrow portions.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{A-VALID} \\
 \top \multimap \exists \gamma. \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q v * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q v \\
 \\
 \text{A-UPDATE-SURPLUS} \\
 \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_p v \multimap \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{p+q} v + w * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w \\
 \\
 \text{A-UPDATE-SURPLUS-CANCEL} \\
 \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{p+q} v + w * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w \multimap \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_p v \\
 \\
 \text{A-UPDATE} \\
 \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_p v + w * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w \multimap \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_p v + w' * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w'
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{A-FRACTIONAL} \\
\gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_{p+q} v + w \dashv\vdash \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_p v * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w \\
\\
\text{A-AGREE} \\
\gamma \overset{\bullet}{\hookrightarrow}_p v * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_q w \text{ -* } v = w \\
\\
\text{A-INCLUDED} \\
\gamma \overset{\bullet}{\hookrightarrow}_n v * \gamma \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_m w \text{ -* } n \geq m > 0
\end{array}$$

Previously we provided our ARC invariant. On the outer layer we make the claim that either the reference count is 0, or the ARC follows a certain memory layout. We enforce that the counter provided to the invariant is the one that actually corresponds to the "true" counter through the use of the outer authoritative view. We are forced to use two different such views because in the inner one we use the counter as the fraction and a fraction of 0 would not be allowed. The inner view holds the fractional value that represents the amount of Φ that is currently borrowed away. Through one additional condition $q_v + q_b = 1$ we enforce that the sum of the borrowed fraction and the fraction currently stored inside of the invariant add up to 1. The ghost variable inside of our invariant is used to ensure that if we open our invariant multiple times and we extract Φ we will receive witnesses parametrized under the same variable.

The definitions for `arcborrow` and `arc` are pretty similar with the distinction that `arcborrow` takes an explicit value instead of keeping it under an existential, and that it does not have a borrowed value of 0 under its second fragment.

While proving the Hoare triples for the ARC we are opening the invariant. There we first have to eliminate the impossible case where the counter is 0 (and therefore the ARC would have been freed). This is done by noticing the contradiction: there is a fragment being held by `arc` and `arcborrow` that contains a value greater than 0 ($\gamma_1 \overset{\circ}{\hookrightarrow}_\pi q_a$, where $q_a \in (0, 1]$). Meanwhile if the counter is zero that would imply that $0 \geq q_a > 0$ which is a contradiction so we can eliminate this case.

LEMMA 4 (ARC IS FRACTIONAL). *We prove it by using G-FRACTIONAL, A-FRACTIONAL, as well as the fact that invariants are fractional.*

7 Related work

Compiler correctness. There have been many efforts to create provably correct compilers. One of the more famous one is `CompCert` by Leroy [14] which is a formally verified C compiler whose entire compilation pipeline has been successfully verified in Rocq. As we mentioned in the introduction the `CompCert` proof is done directly on the operational semantics and they have been able to prove stronger correctness properties, both of which we wanted to avoid for scalability and efficiency reasons. While there are various "strong" properties when it comes to compiler correctness (such as full abstraction or robustness [1]) we decided to only focus on the two weaker properties that we mentioned (safety and semantic type preservation) as we wanted to use a property that can be shown to be true for a compiler in a relatively straightforward manner using in a reasonable amount of time. As a result we did not investigate other safety properties in great detail.

In their work Patterson et al. [18] consider two languages that may be embedded in each other that are compiled into a stack based language. While they do use a logical relation they do not make use of separation logic and instead prove things directly based on the operational semantics of the target language, which can be somewhat unwieldy.

Reference counter. `Rustbelt` [9] formalizes a subset of the Rust programming language. As part of its effort it includes a formalization of an ARC. Their implementation has various features that ours lacks, such as weak references. However we found that their ARC specification is not described in a published paper and it only really exists in Rocq code, so we have not able to provide a direct comparison between our approaches. We leave the investigation to how their ARC specification is related to ours and whether our approach can be used with their ARC as a possible further work.

In their paper Mulder et al. [15] present an ARC formalized in Diaframe, which is a proof automation tool written in Iris. Their solution makes use of a global counter that is kept within the context that asserts the number of tokens (each of which represent one reference) exist. The number used in the counter can be a variable that is stored in our proof context, and therefore one could make a claim that there exist $n + 1$ tokens in existence. This is somewhat similar to the concept of the resource algebra fragments that we used in our implementation, except we do not externalize the ARC counter anywhere. We believe that the global nature of said counter could pose a challenge if it was to be used with our proof, but further investigation is warranted.

Logical relations. Previous works have used logical relations similar to ours that utilize source types to sets of target values [3, 4]. In these papers they also make use of semantic typing however they do not make use of separation logic.

8 Conclusion and future work

We have successfully showed how to formalize a compiler specification from a high level garbage collected language and prove that it is safe. We also implemented and specified an ARC that that we link into our target programs. Our formalization is done in Iris which uses an affine separation logic which as mentioned in Section 4 makes it hard to prove leak-freedom. While we have proven memory safety we have not done the same for leak-freedom, unlike Wagner et al. [23]. There have been some efforts to implement a linear separation logic on top of Iris such as Iron [5] but it would require further evaluation as to whether such systems could be used for our purposes as they make various modifications to the base system (for example in Iron the invariant mechanism is significantly different compared to Iris). There are some other interesting extensions that could be done to our formalization. For example functions could be modified in order to be able to capture closures. Another possibility would be the creation and proof of compliance (Definition 1) of a compiler for **MyLang**, this would require the implementation of a type-checker due to our type-derivation directed way of compilation.

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